

Propagating Time-Dependent Stochastic Uncertainty via Adjoint-based Depletion Perturbation Theory Sensitivity Coefficients in OpenMC

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803235

ABSTRACT

This work extended adjoint-based Depletion Perturbation Theory (DPT) sensitivity coefficients to propagate and estimate the stochastic uncertainty of time-dependent nuclide inventories through depletion simulations of a simplified UO₂ fuel pin in OpenMC. Using sensitivity coefficients of transient nuclide densities with respect to perturbations in reaction rates, restricted to (n, f) and (n, γ) , and immediate prior number densities, this work examined how contributions to DPT uncertainty changed throughout the continuous-energy Monte Carlo (MC) simulation coupled with depletion solvers. The DPT-derived stochastic uncertainty was compared with reference uncertainty estimates obtained from 50 randomly seeded MC runs. Although some disagreement was observed, possibly due to untracked covariances, DPT stochastic uncertainty estimates generally agreed with reference estimates within a factor of approximately two.

Keywords: Adjoint, Depletion, Stochastic, Uncertainty, OpenMC

1. INTRODUCTION

Uncertainty quantification from nuclear reactor depletion modeling is crucial for predicting core performance and composition, developing criticality safety guidelines for waste management and advanced reactors, and scheduling reactor outages for refueling. Continuous-energy Monte Carlo (MC) simulations, such as OpenMC, provide the high-fidelity reaction rates needed to model the evolution of time-dependent inventories and reactor physics properties for advanced reactor concepts and nuclear processes proposing unconventional fuels, irregular geometries, and unique operating parameters. Due to the stochastic nature of MC sampling, uncertainties in estimated reactor physics quantities and nuclide inventories propagate through depletion simulations [1]. This stochastic uncertainty could become amplified through successive depletion time steps, particularly in systems characterized by undersampled fission sources, compact geometries, or novel fuel designs [2, 3].

Stochastic methods for quantifying uncertainty capture nonlinear and temporal effects but require repeated random sampling, resulting in substantial computational expense. Alone, these high-order methods offer little insight into which uncertain inputs most strongly influence predicted nuclide inventories or reactivity. Although Sobol indices can provide information on how variances in various inputs impact output variance, multiple simulation runs are still required. Linear stochastic uncertainty quantification methods based on Depletion Perturbation Theory (DPT) instead use sensitivity coefficients to estimate uncertainty in depletion responses—such as reaction rates, reactivity, or nuclide densities—without the need for repeated MC simulations.

Adjoint-weighted DPT response functions offer a computationally efficient approach to capture fully coupled, time-dependent effects in sensitivity coefficients. Recent work by Murphy and Perfetti [4, 5] introduced an adjoint-based DPT method coupled with Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) to estimate depletion sensitivity coefficients of transient nuclide densities to nuclear data and predicted number densities within continuous-energy MC simulations combined with depletion solvers. This work extends the adjoint-based DPT framework to propagate and estimate stochastic uncertainty through time-dependent depletion simulations of a simplified UO₂ fuel pin, using a limited number of depleting nuclides and reaction types for two compositionally and temporally unique systems. This work compares the DPT-derived relative uncertainties with reference uncertainty estimates obtained from multiple randomly seeded MC runs. Finally, this work examines how contributions to DPT stochastic uncertainty evolve throughout depletion simulations.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Depletion Sensitivity Coefficients

In MC simulations coupled with depletion solvers, neutron transport simulations tally power-normalized, transmutation-relevant reaction rates and the associated stochastic uncertainties for a given nuclide across numerous histories and batches. A depletion solver then uses these tallied reaction rates to integrate the Bateman equation and update the time-dependent number densities, $N(t)$. DPT sensitivity coefficients describe the relative change experienced by some response, such as $N(t)$, with respect to a small perturbation in an arbitrary input parameter, α :

$$S_{N(t),\alpha} = \frac{\partial N(t)/N(t)}{\partial \alpha/\alpha} \quad (1)$$

To quantify the impact of stochastic uncertainty on the evolving nuclide inventories, an adjoint-based DPT approach was employed to compute sensitivity coefficients of nuclide number densities with respect to perturbations in the reaction rates, RR_i , and the immediate prior number densities for all nuclides, $N_{j,t-1}$. These contributions can then be combined to obtain the relative uncertainty in each nuclide's number density:

$$\frac{\sigma(N)}{N} = \sqrt{\sum_i \left(S_{N,RR_i} \frac{\sigma RR_i}{RR_i} \right)^2 + \sum_j \left(S_{N,N_j} \frac{\sigma N_{j,t-1}}{N_{j,t-1}} \right)^2} \quad (2)$$

For simplicity, this work limited RR_i to (n, f) and (n, γ) reaction rates. Due to the sum of squares in Equation 2, overestimations in DPT-derived stochastic uncertainty may occur.

2.2. Experimental Setup

The OpenMC model describes a 3-D, 2.4%-enriched UO_2 fuel pin cell ($r = 0.39$ cm) with a helium gap, zirconium-alloy cladding, and surrounded by borated water with reflected boundaries. Power was maintained at a typical PWR power density of 90 kW/L [6]. The depletion simulations featured two prominent production pathways: (i) a ^{239}Pu production chain modeled with 12 depleting nuclides over a 31-day burn period split into 8 time steps, and (ii) an extended ^{252}Cf production chain modeled with 37 depleting nuclides across a 561-day burn period split into 19 time steps. Both models were geometrically identical, shared the same burn times for the first 8 depletion time steps, and estimated the reference stochastic uncertainty from repeated simulations using 50 different random number seeds.

These simulations used continuous-energy, ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data and the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) exponential-matrix solver for the depletion equations. The computed sensitivity coefficients used 1,000 particles per cycle, 10 inactive cycles, and 5,000 total cycles. To reduce time-discretization errors in short-lived nuclides, DPT sensitivities were accumulated following 16,000 integrated sub-steps between each depletion stage. Table I shows the depletion time steps implemented across both models. Shorter time step intervals were chosen initially to observe the effects of radioisotopes with short half-lives, $t_{1/2}$, as equilibrium levels are reached. These short-lived nuclides included: ^{135}I ($t_{1/2} \sim 6.6$ h), ^{135}Xe ($t_{1/2} \sim 9.2$ h), ^{239}U ($t_{1/2} \sim 23.5$ min), ^{239}Np ($t_{1/2} \sim 2.4$ d), ^{243}Pu ($t_{1/2} \sim 5.0$ h), ^{242}Am ($t_{1/2} \sim 16.0$ h), ^{244}Am ($t_{1/2} \sim 10.0$ h), $^{244\text{m}}\text{Am}$ ($t_{1/2} \sim 26.1$ min), ^{249}Cm ($t_{1/2} \sim 64.2$ min), and ^{250}Bk ($t_{1/2} \sim 3.2$ h).

Table I. Depletion time steps.

Time Step	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Burn Time (d)	0.1	0.3	0.6	1.0	3.0	6.0	10.0	10.0	20.0	20.0
Total Burn (d)	0.1	0.4	1.0	2.0	5.0	11.0	21.0	31.0	51.0	71.0
Time Step	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	
Burn Time (d)	30.0	30.0	30.0	60.0	60.0	60.0	60.0	80.0	80.0	
Total Burn (d)	101.0	131.0	161.0	221.0	281.0	341.0	401.0	481.0	561.0	

To evaluate the adjoint-based DPT method for propagating stochastic uncertainty in time-dependent nuclide inventories, an initial 31-day benchmark test was restricted to the ^{239}Pu activation chain and

common fission products relevant to early PWR irradiation. The analysis was then extended to a 561-day simulation that tracked stochastic uncertainty across longer, more complex, higher-actinide chains relevant to a ^{252}Cf production problem. For both systems, the depleting UO_2 fuel pin contained the following nuclides, where applicable:

1. **Uranium isotopes:** ^{234}U , ^{235}U , and ^{238}U . For both systems, it was assumed that these were the only uranium isotopes present in the fresh UO_2 fuel pin.
2. **Fission products:** ^{135}I , ^{135}Xe , ^{136}Xe , ^{135}Cs , ^{156}Gd , and ^{157}Gd . Both systems featured both long- and short-lived nuclides, as well as both large and small neutron absorption cross sections, to illustrate how varied absorption strengths affected stochastic uncertainty.
3. **^{239}Pu activation chain:** ^{239}U , ^{239}Np , and ^{239}Pu . This triad demonstrated how uncertainty propagated through the short-lived activation products, ^{239}U and ^{239}Np , that were ultimately dependent on the ^{238}U (n, γ) reaction rate.
4. **Higher actinides and the ^{252}Cf activation chain:** ^{239}U , ^{239}Np , ^{239}Pu , ^{240}Pu , ^{241}Pu , ^{242}Pu , ^{243}Pu , ^{244}Pu , ^{241}Am , ^{242}Am , $^{242\text{m}}\text{Am}$, ^{243}Am , ^{244}Am , $^{244\text{m}}\text{Am}$, ^{242}Cm , ^{243}Cm , ^{244}Cm , ^{245}Cm , ^{246}Cm , ^{247}Cm , ^{248}Cm , ^{249}Cm , ^{249}Bk , ^{250}Bk , ^{249}Cf , ^{250}Cf , ^{251}Cf , and ^{252}Cf . This set illustrated how uncertainty propagated across long, branching, capture-decay chains mixed with long- and short-lived nuclides, as well as nuclides capable of spontaneous fission, in a system where Pu increasingly contributes to the fission rate. This set of nuclides was only present in the 561-day simulation.

This analysis compared DPT-derived relative uncertainties against reference estimates alongside trends in the final number densities. Additionally, this analysis decomposed the DPT uncertainty into rate- and inventory-driven fractional contributions for each nuclide in the system.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Comparison of DPT and Reference Relative Uncertainties with Concentration

Comparisons of the relative uncertainties with trending concentrations reveal that the uncertainties tend to spike at the same physically meaningful moments, such as the onset of increased ^{239}Pu production or the rapid succession to secular equilibrium for short-lived nuclides.

3.1.1. Early fission products and the ^{239}Pu activation chain for 31-day depletion simulation

Table II shows the time step at which the maximum absolute difference between the DPT and reference relative uncertainties, the DPT-to-reference ratio at the maximum absolute difference in uncertainties, and the average DPT-to-reference ratio for all nuclides in the 31-day depletion simulation. On average, the DPT and reference relative uncertainties were within a factor of approximately 1.9-3.1.

Table II. Comparison of DPT to reference relative uncertainties for all nuclides in 31-day depletion simulation.

Nuclide	Time Step at Maximum Absolute Difference	DPT/Ref at Maximum Absolute Difference	Average DPT/Ref	Nuclide	Time Step at Maximum Absolute Difference	DPT/Ref at Maximum Absolute Difference	Average DPT/Ref
^{234}U	8	1.03	1.06 ± 0.06	^{157}Gd	7	2.32	1.35 ± 0.64
^{239}U	5	0.73	0.91 ± 0.11	^{239}Pu	3	0.52	0.63 ± 0.13
^{239}Np	5	0.72	0.88 ± 0.12	^{136}Xe	6	2.71	2.14 ± 0.62
^{238}U	8	0.84	0.86 ± 0.08	^{235}U	8	2.57	2.21 ± 0.19
^{135}I	5	0.76	0.82 ± 0.08	^{135}Cs	5	3.88	4.06 ± 1.22
^{156}Gd	2	0.77	0.78 ± 0.08	^{135}Xe	6	5.82	4.43 ± 1.27

The DPT and reference relative uncertainties for ^{234}U , ^{235}U , and ^{238}U were in the order of 10^{-4} - 10^{-6} %, as the abundant U-fuel isotopes depleted slowly, with approximately 99.46%, 99.43%, and 99.98% of the original ^{234}U , ^{235}U , and ^{238}U remaining at the end of the 31-day simulation. The near unity in the DPT-to-reference relative uncertainty ratio reported for ^{234}U and ^{238}U suggests that for abundant, slowly evolving isotopes essentially undergoing single-path transmutations, the linear sensitivity assumptions in DPT relative uncertainty are sufficient.

Figure 1. DPT and reference relative uncertainty estimates for the ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^{239}Pu nuclide densities.

Figure 1 and Table I show that although the ^{235}U uncertainties remained quite small in absolute terms, the DPT uncertainty estimate increased to approximately 2.6 times the reference value by the final time step. In fixed-power simulations with a single dominant fission source, slight decreases in that fission source inventory are normalized by an increased flux, thereby increasing all reaction rates and making ^{235}U more prone to covariances not accounted for in Equation 2. Conversely, reference estimates capture covariances that can reduce the relative uncertainty.

Additionally, the divergence in ^{238}U relative uncertainties begins as the ^{239}Pu inventory accumulates. This suggests that positive covariances between the ^{238}U (n, γ) reaction rate, ^{239}Pu inventory, and the evolving flux could strengthen with burnup. Similarly, while the ^{239}Pu inventory is small, the reference uncertainty estimate reports a broader uncertainty band. However, the bias between the ^{239}Pu relative uncertainties appears to become fixed as the short-lived fission and activation products reach secular equilibrium, and as the ^{239}Pu inventory begins increasing at a constant rate. The fixed offset that settles between the uncertainties may indicate missing covariance terms. Future work will explore methods to track these covariances to improve uncertainty estimates.

3.1.2. Higher actinides and the ^{252}Cf activation chain 561-day depletion simulation

Table II shows the time step at which the maximum absolute difference between the DPT and reference relative uncertainties, the DPT-to-reference ratio at the maximum absolute difference in uncertainties, and the average DPT-to-reference ratio for all nuclides in the 561-day depletion simulation. On average, the DPT and reference relative uncertainties were within a factor of approximately 1.5-2.0.

Table III. Comparison of DPT to reference relative uncertainties for all nuclides in 561-day simulation.

Nuclide	Time Step at Maximum Absolute Difference	DPT/Ref at Maximum Absolute Difference	Average DPT/Ref	Nuclide	Time Step at Maximum Absolute Difference	DPT/Ref at Maximum Absolute Difference	Average DPT/Ref
^{243}Pu	19	1.18	1.00 ± 0.09	^{249}Cm	6	0.56	0.72 ± 0.08
^{234}U	19	0.95	0.96 ± 0.08	$^{242\text{m}}\text{Am}$	18	1.64	1.40 ± 0.16
^{235}U	19	1.05	1.06 ± 0.10	^{247}Cm	18	0.74	0.71 ± 0.06
^{250}Bk	7	0.70	0.88 ± 0.15	^{157}Gd	15	1.91	1.44 ± 0.42
^{243}Am	19	0.88	0.88 ± 0.07	^{240}Pu	19	0.61	0.69 ± 0.07
^{242}Pu	19	0.81	1.14 ± 0.19	^{245}Cm	15	0.64	0.68 ± 0.07
^{135}I	19	1.50	1.21 ± 0.11	^{242}Am	10	1.77	1.48 ± 0.17
^{244}Am	8	0.71	0.81 ± 0.07	^{246}Cm	18	0.70	0.67 ± 0.06
^{238}U	19	0.72	0.81 ± 0.08	^{241}Am	19	1.58	1.51 ± 0.14
^{239}Np	16	0.66	0.80 ± 0.08	^{136}Xe	4	2.08	1.53 ± 0.28
$^{244\text{m}}\text{Am}$	17	0.68	0.79 ± 0.07	^{250}Cf	8	0.42	0.65 ± 0.22
^{251}Cf	8	0.57	0.78 ± 0.17	^{249}Bk	7	0.52	0.64 ± 0.07
^{244}Cm	19	0.77	0.78 ± 0.06	^{243}Cm	19	1.33	1.60 ± 0.38
^{239}U	16	0.61	0.77 ± 0.09	^{239}Pu	10	0.45	0.61 ± 0.10
^{252}Cf	10	0.49	0.76 ± 0.37	^{241}Pu	8	0.46	0.60 ± 0.08
^{242}Cm	17	1.59	1.31 ± 0.17	^{249}Cf	8	0.24	0.36 ± 0.14
^{248}Cm	19	0.73	0.74 ± 0.08	^{135}Cs	5	3.44	2.90 ± 0.72

²⁴⁴ Pu	15	0.66	0.74 ± 0.08	¹³⁵ Xe	6	3.79	3.46 ± 0.64
¹⁵⁶ Gd	8	0.56	0.73 ± 0.08				

This trend of gradual divergence in relative uncertainty estimates as burnup progressed was observed in many of the slowly evolving higher actinides further up the ²⁵²Cf activation chain. This suggests that for largely abundant nuclides with smooth or slowly evolving kinetics, the DPT and reference uncertainties remain small and in relatively good agreement.

Figure 2. DPT and reference relative uncertainty for ²³⁵U, ²³⁸U, and ²⁴³Am nuclide number densities.

Figure 2 shows the relative uncertainties alongside trends in the predicted concentrations for ²³⁵U, ²³⁸U, and ²⁴³Am. The DPT and reference uncertainties for ²³⁴U, ²³⁵U, and ²³⁸U revealed strong agreement, with the DPT-to-reference uncertainty ratio near unity. Since ²³⁵U is sharing more of the initial fission load, the response sensitivity for ²³⁵U reduced as the normalized flux distributes importance across more channels. For long-lived nuclides that essentially follow single-path kinetics, uncertainty is dominated by smooth inventory carryover with slight production-removal or rate-flux covariances.

Figure 3. DPT and reference relative uncertainties for ¹³⁶Xe and ¹⁵⁷Gd nuclide number densities.

DPT overestimations reflect where negative covariances, such as production-removal anticorrelations, would otherwise reduce the net variance in a nuclide’s inventory. For stable fission products that are strongly influenced by rapid capture/decay chains or strong absorption cross sections, such as ¹³⁶Xe and ¹⁵⁷Gd, respectively, in Figure 3, the large sensitivity coefficients to various reaction rates lead to large uncertainties early, while the reference reflects negatively correlated channels that cancel out variance and pull the uncertainty down. Generally, once the source(s) of the nuclide become more certain, and concentration changes become constant, the relative uncertainties begin to stabilize with a persistent offset bias in the as sensitivity coefficients plateau.

Figure 4. DPT and reference relative uncertainties for ^{135}I , ^{243}Pu , and ^{249}Cm nuclide number densities.

The lifetime of short-lived nuclides is often comparable to, or shorter than, the depletion time steps. For short-lived nuclides, such as ^{135}I , ^{243}Pu , and ^{249}Cm in Figure 4, fast production-decay kinetics quickly dominate, and the nuclides rapidly reach secular or quasi-equilibrium. While the DPT-derived uncertainties appear relatively stable once sensitivities plateau as equilibrium is reached, random fluctuations in the normalized flux and tallied rates promptly affecting the nuclide’s predicted number density are reflected in the reference estimates.

Figure 5. DPT and reference relative uncertainty for ^{241}Pu and ^{252}Cf nuclide number densities.

Figure 5 shows the relative uncertainties with trends in concentration for ^{241}Pu and ^{252}Cf . A constant bias between the relative uncertainties could indicate a missing positive covariance in the linear DPT sensitivity. The relative uncertainties appear to fluctuate in response to low-concentration noise for many late-chain products with relatively slow increases in concentration initially, such as ^{252}Cf . Once the late chain nuclides become established, both relative uncertainties begin to stabilize. Overall, this approach for determining stochastic uncertainty could become useful for characterizing long activation chains common in spent-fuel processes.

3.2. Fractional Contributions to Stochastic Uncertainty

The stochastic uncertainties for the predicted number density were decomposed into the two fractional contributions: (i) the previous number density uncertainty, and (ii) the current reaction rate uncertainties. The DPT stochastic uncertainties are initially determined entirely by the reaction rate sensitivities for all nuclides because prior number density uncertainties have not yet been computed.

3.2.1. Fractional contributions for 31-day depletion simulation

The 31-day validation tests revealed that DPT uncertainty in short-lived nuclides was dominated by reaction-rate uncertainty contributions nearly instantaneously. In contrast, fractional contributions to DPT uncertainty for the U-fuel isotopes appeared to be increasingly dominated by previous number density uncertainties. The short depletion window limited drawing further conclusions.

3.2.2. Fractional contributions for 561-day depletion simulation

During debugging, this work observed interesting insights by examining the fractional contribution to stochastic uncertainty at each depletion step from reaction rates in that step versus stochastic

uncertainty that had propagated from reaction rates in previous time steps. From the 561-day test, DPT uncertainty for short-lived nuclides remained completely dominated by reaction rate uncertainty contributions nearly instantly. However, an oscillatory pattern resembling “shark fins” was observed in many of the nuclides. To examine the oscillatory behavior, three depletion simulations were carried out, with the burn time span halved at each time step. That is, the three depletion simulations were run with 2x, 4x, and 8x the time steps specified in the original test specifications outlined in Table I. For many nuclides, it was noted that these oscillations resolved into 11 distinct shark fin patterns, with each fin corresponding to a change in the span of the time-step interval. For example, moving from a 1-day time step to a 2-day time step.

As such, these shark fins do not indicate a deficiency in the DPT stochastic propagation algorithm. However, this oscillatory pattern did interfere with interpreting how the fractional contributions to DPT uncertainty evolved for each nuclide throughout the depletion simulation. To avoid the shark-fin pattern, Figures 6 and 7 include results for reaction rate uncertainty contributions from a simulation using evenly spaced time steps in log-time. This suggests that using evenly spaced log-time intervals may allow for a more intuitive interpretation of DPT uncertainty contributions as isotopes approach equilibrium. This raises an interesting question of whether standard, non-DPT-depletion simulations could improve the accuracy of their isotope predictions by using evenly spaced log-time steps.

Figure 6. Reaction rate fractional contribution to ^{135}I and ^{235}U number density stochastic uncertainties.

Figure 6 shows the reaction rate fractional contributions to DPT uncertainty for a short-lived nuclide, such as ^{135}I , and for nuclides not governed by instant production-decay kinetics, such as ^{235}U . The reaction rate fractional contribution curve from the evenly spaced time grid provided a smooth interpretation for the results. Reaction rate uncertainty contributions to DPT quickly dominate short-lived nuclides because the evolution of these isotopes is governed by instantaneous rate feedback rather than accumulated nuclide inventories. For all other nuclides, previous number density uncertainties contribute most to DPT uncertainty estimates. For short-lived nuclides, reaction rate uncertainty contributions quickly become the main drivers of DPT uncertainty shortly after fractional contributions from previous number density uncertainties to ^{235}U DPT proportionally stabilize.

Figure 7. Reaction rate fraction contributions to ^{157}Gd and ^{252}Cf number density stochastic uncertainties.

Figure 7 shows the reaction rate fractional contributions to ^{157}Gd and ^{252}Cf number density stochastic uncertainties. Although ^{157}Gd is not a short-lived nuclide, reaction rate uncertainties ultimately dominate the fractional contribution to DPT uncertainty as quasi-equilibrium is reached. Additionally,

these results can reflect noise in the fractional contributions to DPT uncertainty, such as early in the ^{252}Cf depletion simulation when inventory is low and stochastic uncertainty is high.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Using adjoint-based DPT sensitivity coefficients in OpenMC, this work develops a method to estimate the contribution of stochastic uncertainty to predicted nuclide number densities in MC depletion simulations. The models evaluated in this work, as referenced in the Methods section, reported DPT and reference stochastic uncertainty estimates in relatively good agreement. The best agreement between uncertainties was observed in the latter system, which hosted more species, spread importance from the initial fission load across more channels, and reported that the number density uncertainties were within a factor of approximately 1.5-2.0. For both systems, abundant nuclides with smooth or slowly evolving concentrations reported the best agreement between DPT and reference uncertainties.

Agreement between DPT and the reference relative uncertainty trends suggests that this method could be sufficient for estimating uncertainty in time-dependent parameters in reactor depletion simulations. Discrepancies in stochastic uncertainties may result from untracked correlations and will be explored in future work. Brown has noted that undersampling the fission source and related transport statistics can lead to discrepancies in tally-based uncertainties, with reference measurements differing by as much as a factor of three [7]. Although the pin-cell model presented in this work is far less complex than the large, full-core reactor simulations where this effect is most common, it is interesting that the difference factor observed by Brown is similar to the factor of 1.5-2.0 discrepancy observed in this work.

Although approximate, this work reports a computationally efficient approach to estimate stochastic uncertainty ranging over several orders of magnitude in depletion simulations. Furthermore, this method provides unique insight into the components that drive the propagated uncertainty. Additionally, these results suggest that incorporating evenly spaced time grids, or exploring adaptive time stepping, could be useful for depletion simulations. Finally, future work will extend this OpenMC depletion sensitivity analysis method to estimate the sensitivity of spent fuel isotopic inventories to additional uncertain responses, such as k_{eff} and β_{eff} .

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was performed using funds from the Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) Research and Development Grant under award number 31310024M0017.

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